

About Jay's Bus Service

Jay's Bus Service provides [premier school bus service](#) for schools, camps and charter trips. Our primary purpose is to transport students to and from school safely, efficiently and dependably, to provide the highest quality of support for the educational programs by delivering the best possible transportation services.

We provide transportation to schools and camps of all sizes; we transport groups from 10 to 1000+. Our company has plenty of short- and long-term transportation contracts, both privately and commercially. At Jay's Bus Service, we are committed to customer satisfaction. This means that we work tirelessly to ensure that our customers are 100% satisfied!

Jay's Bus Service cares deeply about its drivers and its passengers, and we make it our mission to spread an air of community and belonging throughout whomever we serve. We want to provide you with reliable, timely, and above all, safe, bus service. We make both our drivers and passengers feel like family, an experience that's more personable than the kind a large bus corporation can give.

Jay's Bus Service is led by an experienced management team that delivers customized solutions that meet the needs of the community. Each employee at Jay's is given a pre-employment list of requirements which they must pass before they are hired.

It is our goal to provide a safe, efficient pupil transportation service. To accomplish this goal, there are responsibilities and rules for each member involved in the transportation system, staff, students and parents. We ask parents to become familiar with the rules and procedures and to discuss them with their child.

[Jay's Bus Service](#) is privileged to be transporting New Jersey's future. Jay's works with schools and camps of all sizes; we transport groups ranging from 10 to 1000+ passengers. We provide plenty of short and long term transportation contracts, both privately and commercially. At Jay's Bus Service, YOUR satisfaction is our priority. We work tirelessly to create a complete picture of 100% customer satisfaction!